

The science of well-being: An integrative approach to mental health in Academia

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Indicate your track:

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1. Scientific and practitioners' research presentations
 - a. Bottom-up and community-driven interventions
 - b. Institutional interventions and policies
 - c. Policy-Level insights
2. Workshop/hands-on practices for enhancing researcher mental health and well-being

Purpose

According to the ReMO Researcher Mental Health and Well-being Manifesto, there is a growing consensus for governments and institutions to consider mental health and well-being as top priorities. If societies and organizations want to be effective promoters of well-being and mental health, then a clear understanding of the mechanisms through which individuals can adapt to their environments, in a healthy and happy way, is paramount. Put differently, to promote well-being and mental health in academia it is vital to adopt empirically validated frameworks that accurately capture the dynamics involved in well-being and mental health. By doing so, it will be possible to develop effective person-centered approaches to mental health that include policies and institutional practices that are tailored to the promotion of well-being.

Cloninger's biopsychosocial model of personality (which is strongly grounded in research from neurobiology, psychology, anthropology, genetics, evolutionary biology, and the social sciences) is arguably one of the most robustly validated frameworks for conceptualizing adaptive and maladaptive human functioning. This model has the strength of describing the interactions among the biological, psychological, social, and spiritual dimensions of experience that are known to favor well-being, and has been widely demonstrated to be an excellent predictor of human functioning in its various expressions. Research has shown, for example, that this model accounts for substantial variance in maladaptive functioning in clinical and 'normative' community samples, but also explains significant

variance in expressions of adaptive functioning and human flourishing. Indeed, studies show this model is strongly predictive of human capacities for creativity, longevity, pro-social behavior, self-awareness, positive adaptation different challenges, positive mental health and well-being.

In this talk, we will discuss the potential of Cloninger's biopsychosocial model as a conceptual framework for understanding the well-being and mental health of academics and university staff, including their ability to thrive when confronted with the challenges of academia. Because this model describes the processes that underlie well-being in all people – regardless of their age, culture, or gender – in any setting, it is readily applicable to academia. We will describe how this model offers an empirically validated framework that can promote the recognition of mental health and well-being; and a person-centered approach to training, career management, and the promotion of well-being within academia. More specifically, we will outline how Cloninger's model allows for an clear understanding of the dynamics underlying mental health and well-being, and how major indicators of well-being -- negative affect, positive affect and life satisfaction – depend on different integrations of biopsychosocial dimensions.

Finally, we consider the potential of a person-centered biopsychosocial well-being coaching intervention, based on Cloninger's approach, in the context of academic, including in doctoral training programs and in organizational approaches to promoting positive mental health and well-being. This intervention has been empirically shown to increase overall mental and physical health, happiness, life satisfaction, sense of accomplishment, energy level, and social and family life satisfaction in various types of professional, but not yet in the context of academia. Thus, in summary, in this talk we address the following question: How can a person-centered biopsychosocial approach to well-being and mental health and associated coaching intervention benefit those who work in academia?

Resources

- Cloninger CR (2004). *Feeling Good: The Science of Well-Being*. New York, Oxford University Press.
- Cloninger CR, Zohar AH, Cloninger KM. (2010). Promotion of Well-being in Person-centered Mental Health Care. *Focus*, 8:165-179.
- Cloninger, C. R. (2006). The science of well-being: an integrated approach to mental health and its disorders. *World psychiatry*, 5(2), 71.
- Cloninger, C. R. (2013). What makes people healthy, happy, and fulfilled in the face of current world challenges?. *Mens Sana Monographs*, 11(1), 16.
- Cloninger, C. R., & Cloninger, K. M. (2013). People create health: effective health promotion is a creative process. *International journal of person centered medicine*, 3(2), 114.
- Cloninger, C. R., & Zohar, A. H. (2011). Personality and the perception of health and happiness. *Journal of affective disorders*, 128(1-2), 24-32.

- Cloninger, C. R., Salloum, I. M., & Mezzich, J. E. (2012). The dynamic origins of positive health and wellbeing. *International Journal of Person Centered Medicine*, 2(2), 179.
- Cloninger, K. M., & Cloninger, C. R. (2020). The psychobiology of the path to a joyful life: implications for future research and practice. *The Journal of Positive Psychology*, 15(1), 74-83.
- Eley, D.S., Cloninger, C.R., Walters, L., Laurence, C., Synnott, R., Wilkinson, D. (2013). The relationship between resilience and personality traits in doctors: implications for enhancing well being. *PeerJ*, 1: 3216. <http://doi.org/10.777/peerj.216.eCollection>
- Eley, D. S., Leung, J., Hong, B. A., Cloninger, K. M., & Cloninger, C. R. (2016). Identifying the dominant personality profiles in medical students: implications for their well-being and resilience. *PloS one*, 11(8), e0160028.
- Josefsson, K., Cloninger, C. R., Hintsanen, M., Jokela, M., Pulkki-Råback, L., & Keltikangas-Järvinen, L. (2011). Associations of personality profiles with various aspects of well-being: a population-based study. *Journal of affective disorders*, 133(1-2), 265-273.
- Moreira, P. A., Inman, R. A., & Cloninger, C. R. (2021). Virtues in action are related to the integration of both temperament and character: Comparing the VIA classification of Virtues and Cloninger's biopsychosocial model of personality. *The Journal of Positive Psychology*, 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439760.2021.1975158>
- Moreira, P.A.S., Inman, R.A. & Cloninger, C.R. (Submitted, Under Review). *Disentangling the Personality Pathways to Well-being*. Manuscript Submitted for Publication.
- Zwir, I., Del-Val, C., Arnedo, J., Pulkki-Råback, L., Konte, B., Yang, S. S., ... & Cloninger, C. R. (2021). Three genetic-environmental networks for human personality. *Molecular psychiatry*, 26(8), 3858-3875.
- Zwir, I., Del-Val, C., Hintsanen, M., Cloninger, K. M., Romero-Zaliz, R., Mesa, A., ... & Cloninger, C. R. (2021). Evolution of genetic networks for human creativity. *Molecular psychiatry*, 1-23.